

OpenArchaeo: a Semantic Web Portal to Ease Querying Federated Archaeological Datasets

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ABSTRACT

OpenArchaeo is a semantic-web platform dedicated to archaeology, developed by MASApplus, a french Research Infrastructure Huma-Num consortium, to federate archaeological information scattered in heterogeneous silos, thus building links between datasets.

We present its ontology, representing the key entities in the field of archaeology. Information about places, chronology, people or physical object typology uses controlled vocabularies, ensuring that each dataset contains disambiguated information and scientific terms that are shared and reusable by the community. Links between the datasets are established through both the ontology and the controlled vocabularies.

Datasets in OpenArchaeo are thus structured as knowledge graphs and managed in an online triplestore providing a public query endpoint. We explain the workflow for generating these knowledge graphs from legacy datasets.

For humans, an intuitive visual querying interface was developed, which allows archaeologists to query the datasets using their domain knowledge, without needing to be familiar with the Semantic Web or the underlying ontology. We introduce this visual querying interface dedicated to archaeologists.

Regarding machines, OpenArchaeo was built with the idea that there might be a federation of such portals, which could be queried from any one of them. That is why its code, including the visual interface, is publicly available for reuse.

OpenArchaeo is an Open Data portal: it increases the value of research data by making it easy to find and access on the web, in line with the two first FAIR principles. The use of semantic technologies, standard ontologies and controlled vocabularies meets their requirements for interoperability, and reusability. Moreover, creating links between siloed heterogeneous datasets increases opportunities for reuse.

Keywords: Archeology, Linked Open Data, Open Data Portal, FAIR principles, Semantic Web, CIDOC-CRM, Ontology, Controlled Vocabulary

I- Introduction

OpenArchaeo is a Semantic Web platform dedicated to archaeology, developed by the Huma-Num MASApplus consortium, to federate archaeological information scattered in a large number of heterogeneous silos, thus building links between datasets (Marlet et al., 2019). OpenArchaeo is also an Open Data portal, it increases the value of datasets produced by research by making them

44 easy to find, access and query, in line with the two first FAIR principles (Wilkinson, Dummontier et
45 al. 2016). The use of standard ontologies and the controlled linked open vocabularies used for
46 generating the knowledge graphs hosted in this platform meets the requirements for
47 interoperability, enabling the original legacy datasets to be reused, which complete the two last
48 FAIR principles. Based on Semantic Web technologies, it also ticks the 5 stars of Linked Open
49 Data (Berners-Lee 2006).

50

51 To the best of our knowledge, there is no other semantic platform quite like OpenArchaeo. Very
52 Large Open Data portals exist in archaeology, such as DANS Data Station Archaeology, ADS or
53 ARIADNE, but they contain (links to) legacy datasets in row data formats, such as pdf, csv, json
54 or xml. If they offer to query metadata of these datasets, and access for downloading some of
55 them, they do not allow users for querying directly the datasets themselves, even less to query
56 simultaneously several of them. Moreover, while ADS and ARIADNE do use Semantic Web for
57 managing metadata of datasets, and the corresponding knowledge graphs can be queried in
58 SPARQL, which is the knowledge graph equivalent of SQL for relational databases, you can only
59 use some predefined forms and facets if you don't master their internal semantic model or the
60 SPARQL language. Rather than simply bringing together a vast number of open datasets,
61 OpenArchaeo's aim is to enable the joint use of different datasets through the Semantic Web
62 technologies and shared semantic artefacts, for both computer programmes and human users.
63 More precisely, it is built for allowing archaeologists, and programs developed for archaeologists,
64 to query different archaeological datasets in a shared common way, linking them thanks to a pivot
65 semantic model and widely used controlled vocabularies. For humans, it offers an interface for
66 building visual queries that draws on common concepts in archaeology. These queries are
67 automatically translated to SPARQL using the internal semantic model, that the user does not
68 need to know.

69 When conceptualising the OpenArchaeo platform, a solution was devised by using a semantic
70 model based on the CIDOC CRM (Bekiari et al., 2024), a standard ontology for the integration of
71 cultural heritage data, for representing the key entities in field archaeology. Information relating to
72 places, chronology, people or physical object typology uses public thesauri such as Pactols
73 (Nouvel et al. 2021), and controlled vocabularies as GeoNames, PeriodO, IdRef, VIAF or ORCID,
74 ensuring that each dataset contains disambiguated information and scientific terms that are shared
75 and reusable by the community. Standard ontologies and linked open controlled vocabularies allow
76 us to create links between the datasets hosted in OpenArchaeo. Data is thus structured as a
77 knowledge graph, in RDF format, and managed in an online searchable triplestore, which is hosted
78 by the french Research Infrastructure Huma-Num.

79 However, querying a triplestore requires using the SPARQL query language. In addition, some
80 choices in CIDOC CRM, justified by the goal of integration and interoperability (making links
81 between datasets), makes it rather difficult to query the graphs created using this model. Some
82 information often seen as simple attributes of an entity may in fact be represented by a chain of
83 properties in the CIDOC CRM model. For these reasons, a visual query interface was developed
84 for OpenArchaeo, then made generic under the name Sparnatural by the Sparna company
85 (Francart, 2023). This solution was initially inspired by the interface proposed by ResearchSpace
86 for the British Museum (Oldman and Tanase 2018). It is an intuitive visual semantic query system.
87 Sparnatural allows users to interact with federated triplestores without any specific knowledge of
88 the ontology, the underlying model, or the SPARQL language. Archaeologists can query federated
89 triplestores OpenArchaeo using the archaeological concepts they are used to manipulate, and the
90 application transforms these concepts into their ontological equivalents, to generate the right
91 SPARQL query (Marlet, Francart, Markhoff and Rodier 2019).

92 OpenArchaeo is an innovative and powerful open-source application that enables data
93 published as knowledge graphs to be used not only by machines but also directly by
94 archaeologists, thanks to Sparnatural. This portal of open data increases the value of research
95 data by making it easy to find and access, in line with the first FAIR principles. In addition, thanks
96 to the use of semantic technologies and standard domain ontologies, the datasets presented in

97 OpenArcheo are accessible via a single access point, interoperable thanks to the CIDOC CRM
98 ontology and controlled vocabularies, and reusable by applications via the triplestore access point.
99 We present OpenArcheo in this paper in order to get more feedback from the community, to
100 assess the relevance of Sparnatural's configuration, to explain the dataset integration process, in
101 order to improve the services offered by the platform, increase the number of datasets available
102 and the number of their users, and even, may be, the number of such portals. The rest of this
103 paper is structured as follows: we first present the ontological model on which OpenArcheo relies,
104 and how it guides the workflow for generating knowledge graphs from legacy data. Then we
105 present the benefits of Sparnatural, after which we explain the portal's features, in particular how
106 it allows to query several federated knowledge graphs, before concluding.

107 **II- Model for a common structure and a common expression**

108 The initial work of MASApplus was to support archaeological researchers in publishing their data
109 on the Semantic Web, but this firstly meant starting by making the data accessible as resources
110 on the Web. When this data was put online, it was found to be very heterogeneous in terms of
111 systems, structures and vocabularies. Standardising the vocabularies was a priority for MASApplus,
112 because the concepts used in these datasets need to be aligned with reference vocabularies for
113 the data to be interoperable (places, individuals, periods, subjects and themes). In 2009, Robert
114 Kummer had already highlighted the importance of archaeological data interoperability and the
115 contributions of the Semantic Web (Kummer 2010). The use of OpenRefine free software was
116 invaluable in this task: in addition to data cleaning and homogenisation processes, OpenRefine
117 offers several solutions for enriching data with various reference vocabularies (GeoNames,
118 Pactols, IDRef...).

119 However, the heterogeneity of vocabularies is not the only pitfall: although most of the
120 databases deal with the same archaeological concepts, there is a great variety of structures in
121 these datasets that makes building interoperability bridges between each structure impossible on
122 a community level. Datasets come in the form of XML files, relational databases or tabular files,
123 each with its own structure defined by the researcher or project that produced it. Although the main
124 subjects of these datasets are similar, the heterogeneity of their formats, structures, and models
125 hinders the ability to query them simultaneously. To facilitate the aggregation of heterogeneous
126 datasets, a common data structure had to be created.

127 Semantic web technologies then became the obvious choice. They ease cross-querying of
128 several initially heterogeneous datasets. These datasets deal with archaeology but on a variety of
129 scales, with data that is sometimes detailed, sometimes synthetic, and with unique issues (Marlet
130 et al. 2015). When the OpenArcheo platform was being designed, the chosen solution issues
131 (Marlet et al. 2019) has been to implement a generic model extracted from CIDOC CRM, the
132 ontology ecosystem for cultural heritage (Bekiari, et al. 2024). The relevance of the choice of
133 CIDOC CRM is demonstrated by its use by most European projects on heritage and by major
134 institutions such as the BnF or the British Museum (Niccolucci, Felicetti 2018). OpenArcheo's
135 semantic model is a partial selection of entities and properties from the core CIDOC and some
136 elements from official extensions required to capture the main concepts of archaeology: CRMsci
137 for scientific observations (Doerr, Kritsotaki, et al. 2023), CRMarchaeo for field archaeology
138 (Christoki, Doerr, et al. 2024) and CRMba for archaeological buildings (Ronzino, Niccolucci et al.
139 2016). It represents the key entities of the archaeological domain, such as archaeological sites,
140 archaeological discoveries/excavations, artefacts, stratigraphic units, buildings, archaeological
141 features (walls, graves, postholes, pits, etc.) and archaeological documentation (e.g. record
142 sheets, photographs, drawings). No entities or properties were created for the purposes of
143 OpenArcheo model: everything is taken from CIDOC, thus ensuring better interoperability with
144 European projects that also use this ontology. This model, presented in detail below, can be
145 downloaded (in OWL format) from the [Catalogue page of the OpenArcheo portal](#).

146

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147

Figure 1 - OpenArcheo CIDOC CRM generic model including only key entities.

148

Main classes and relationships in the OpenArcheo model are the discovery (or excavation),
 149 the site, the person responsible for the operation, the location, the structure, the archeological
 150 feature, the stratigraphic unit, and the archaeological material (Figure 1). On this basis, each entity
 151 can be identified, named, typed, and described, and can also be documented and dated, leading
 152 to a complete generic model for describing most of archaeological data (Figure 2).

153

154

Figure 2 - Complete OpenArcheo CIDOC CRM generic model.

155

Thanks to the methodology behind the CIDOC CRM ontology, the creation of relationships
 156 between each identified key entity leads to an enrichment of the data structure. This way, some

157 information, although only implicit in the source, is represented, formalized and used in the
 158 modelling. An example is the representation of the dating of a piece of artefact, which would
 159 correspond to a simple “date” attribute in a more conventional structure, but which becomes a set
 160 of several entities in the CIDOC CRM model (Figure 3).

161

162 **Figure 3** - CIDOC CRM modelling of dating for physical entities in the OpenArcheo model.

163 These entities specify that an event linked to this piece of artefact is dated, oftenly interpreted
 164 as its use, and that this event is linked to a time interval, which can finally be specified as having
 165 one or more dates, depending on the dating method used in the source or the event to be dated
 166 (production, use, discovery, etc.). For example, a coin does not in itself have a date. The date it
 167 bears, sometimes engraved, is that of its production (entry into circulation), but the archaeologist
 168 will only retain a post-quem date and will indicate in his database the dates of use of the coin (from
 169 its production to its disappearance). However, in the database, the archaeologist generally only
 170 indicates “date” for the field name, which is too ambiguous. With a CIDOC-CRM based model, the
 171 date is necessarily linked to an event (a temporal entity), itself linked to the artefact; the artefact
 172 cannot be directly associated with a date. This is an important contribution of the CIDOC: forcing
 173 the implicit to be made explicit.

174 Over and above this apparent (but relevant) rigidity, the CIDOC also offers a degree of flexibility
 175 that makes it possible to adapt to the various situations that can be encountered in archaeological
 176 datasets, mainly because of the scales of representation that can vary. For example, in a corpus
 177 of field recordings, we will specify that the artefacts were found in a stratigraphic unit, possibly in
 178 a feature, itself in a structure and itself in a site. On a regional study scale, which produces an
 179 inventory of the material found on archaeological sites, we will not necessarily specify the
 180 stratigraphic units or the features in which the material was found (Figure 4). For example,
 181 regarding the current datasets in OpenArcheo, compared to an excavation database such as
 182 ArSol, the AERBA corpus is an inventory that does not deal with the scale of the Stratigraphic Unit;
 183 the I-Cerammm corpus focuses mainly on pottery and its context; OUTAGR is an inventory of ancient
 184 artefacts located by site; the Sanctuaires du Limousin inventory is structured on a regional scale,
 185 etc.

186

187
188 **Figure 4** - Example of using different entities according to 4 datasets in OpenArcheo.

189 Semantically, it is simpler in certain corpuses to define that the excavation of a site did indeed
190 exist if a piece of artefact is linked to the site, despite the absence of information about the
191 excavation, than to infer in which stratigraphic unit the artefact was found, if the information is not
192 present.

193 In addition, in many databases the event of excavation or discovery is not explicitly indicated
194 and associated artefacts, archaeological features and structures are directly linked to the site. This
195 combines the two notions of site and operation in the same concept, which can sometimes be
196 justified for practical reasons when an archaeological site is only concerned by a single operation,
197 but this is not always the case. The model represents this event (excavation, discovery) with the
198 S19 Encounter Event class, which is either induced or represented in the archaeological data.

199 Furthermore, although the content of a dataset may be more specific than the entities in the
200 CIDOC CRM model, it can still be described using one of these entities. In this way, the CIDOC
201 CRM model can aggregate objects that are deeply differentiated in their original sources. For
202 example, in CIDOC, the notion of a trail left by humans (E25 Human-made Feature) is generic and
203 encompasses features (pits, postholes, ditches), but also burials or walls (including the foundation
204 trench). It is therefore necessary to distinguish between them, as most archaeological datasets
205 treat these elements as different concepts. In the CIDOC model, precision is then provided by
206 typing (E55 Type): a type is associated with each element (feature, wall, burial), based on a
207 vocabulary/thesaurus defining each of these terms. It should be noted that the notion of "feature"
208 is described by excluding other more specific features such as burials and walls (which are
209 themselves also features).

210 Similarly, the absence of specific entities to represent ceramics, lithic elements or coins is
211 compensated by the possibility of typing a generic entity to specify its original nature (Figure 5). In
212 the example in this figure, the object (named 'Monnaie' in French) is an E22 Human-made Object
213 whose type is 'coin' (as defined by nomisma.org) which is itself an E55 type in CIDOC.

214

215

Figure 5 - Representation of a coin in CIDOC-CRM.

216 The OpenArcheo generic model uses this representation to preserve the specific details of
 217 each object, or the type expressed in the source dataset, with controlled vocabularies such as
 218 Pactols and the Getty AAT (which implementation is discussed below). This approach not only
 219 enriches the data with alignment work but also ensures the interoperability of datasets within the
 220 Semantic Web, thanks to a common structure provided by the CIDOC CRM generic model, and a
 221 common expression provided using controlled vocabularies and other referentials. For entities
 222 such as places, periods, people or organisations we use referential resources such as GeoNames,
 223 PeriodO, IdRef, VIAF or ORCID, which ensure that each knowledge graph contains disambiguated
 224 information and common scientific expressions in their domains.

225

226 Thanks to these two data modelling methods (the description of events and the characterization
 227 of generic classes by external controlled vocabularies), each dataset can be cross-referenced
 228 conceptually through the fundamental questions: Who, What, How, When, Where and Why. To
 229 apply them, a workflow has been devised, where the transformation of heterogeneous legacy
 230 datasets into a homogeneously queryable set of knowledge graphs is described as a sequence of
 231 steps. This workflow has been published in the DARIAH SSH Open Marketplace (Figure 6). It
 232 enables field records such as ArSol (Le Goff et al. 2014), excavation inventories such as
 233 Archaeology in Greece Online (École française d'Athènes) and other French aggregators such as
 234 ArkeOpen to be expressed in the same structure and with the same expression, making
 235 OpenArcheo a powerful portal for accessing archaeological data (Marlet, Roulet, Hivert, Markhoff,
 236 Rodier et al. 2021).

237

238 In opposition to large Open Data platforms, dataset ingestion in OpenArcheo requires much
 239 more effort from the data producer than just providing some very general metadata. OpenArcheo
 240 is a platform made by researchers for researchers. As dataset producers, only Researchers can
 241 warrant that the semantics added to be shared consistently with others is correct. The terms and
 242 the meanings assigned to them are of paramount importance in accurately reflecting the
 243 researcher's production. This is why, as explained in what follows, the OpenArcheo dataset
 244 ingestion workflow relies not only on efficient tools but also systematically on archaeologist
 245 expertise.

246

247 **Figure 6** - MASAplus Consortium workflow for publishing data on OpenArcheo (Katsianis et al. 2023).

248 Each tool used in this workflows is free, open-source, and has online documentation.

249 To ensure that this workflow runs smoothly, data should be cleaned to eliminate incorrect
 250 entries, and enriched by matching with controlled vocabularies. The enrichment with controlled
 251 vocabularies should be handled by the data producers, or a data scientist supervised by an expert
 252 of the domain, in order to preserve the scientific expression of the data. It is the most time-
 253 consuming step of the workflow, depending on the dataset developpement stage: it is easier to
 254 plan the enrichment of a dataset during its creation than to revisit a finalised dataset. In addition,
 255 the data must be published online, so that the URLs of each entity can identify a resource, on the
 256 Web. Indeed, the generic OpenArcheo model requires omitting certain details (e.g. coin weight),
 257 but this information is still accessible via URLs linking to the original resources. The mapping step
 258 between the structure of the dataset and the OpenArcheo model involves defining direct or
 259 interpreted correspondences between their respective schemas. These correspondences are
 260 defined by a semantic web expert (a more specific data scientist), with the help of data producers
 261 who give clues on the semantics behind the dataset original structure. Then, a mapping tool is used
 262 (3M for XML based dataset or Protégé-Ontop for relationnal database) to transform the data into
 263 triples, based on these correspondances. Once the knowledge graph has been generated, checks
 264 are carried out using SHACL rules (Boneva 2017). SHACL is a W3C recommendation to represent
 265 constraints that must be satisfied by a knowledge graph. The ontological model is intended for
 266 logical reasoning, whereas the SHACL rules are for validating data (in the same way as one can
 267 validate an XML document with respect to an XML schema). OpenArcheo's SHACL rules can be
 268 downloaded from the portal's Catalogue page. The validated knowledge graph can then be put
 269 online using a triplestore, i.e. a data management system dedicated to knowledge graphs.
 270 OpenArcheo uses the GraphDB solution (open-source component version), this is the choice of
 271 the French research infrastructure Huma-Num that hosts this knowledge graph manager and
 272 server. However, as OpenArcheo's architecture is modular, it would be entirely feasible to deploy
 273 it with other triplestores such as Qlever, Blazegraph, or Fuzeki.

274 Implementing this workflow requires mastery of several softwares. It is clear that the time
275 required to learn these programs is not necessarily compatible with field archaeology. This
276 workflow is therefore more suited to archaeological research laboratories, which are responsible
277 for supporting their colleagues in preventive archaeology in the use of this process.

278 From here, a client application can send a request to the triplestore endpoint (called SPARQL
279 Endpoint) and receive the elements queried in the knowledge graphs in response. For humans, it
280 is also possible to query the dataset via the SPARQL endpoint, where examples of SPARQL
281 queries are provided for beginners. However, not everyone is familiar with SPARQL, which is why
282 OpenArcheo incorporates Sparnatural.

283 **III- Sparnatural for easing querying of the Semantic Web**

284 Sparnatural was initially (2019) inspired by ResearchSpace (Oldman and Tanase 2018), which
285 enables the British Museum's collections to be queried using CIDOC CRM. Sparnatural then went
286 further by offering an interface based on archaeological concepts, replacing CIDOC classes with
287 concepts that archaeologists are familiar with. To our knowledge, there is no similar open-source
288 initiative. Open Context (Kansa 2026) is a solution offering similar features for archaeologists, but
289 it is a proprietary solution and paid service. The German NFDI project (launched in 2020) has
290 several points in common with our project for cultural heritage as a whole, but has developed its
291 own ontology and vocabularies, which makes this solution less interoperable (Sack et al. 2023).
292 The open-source Sparnatural solution has since been adopted by the Archives Nationales de
293 France (Clavaud, Charbonnier 2022), the Bibliothèque nationale de France, by Huma-Num for
294 cataloging Nakala resources. and several European projects.

295 Querying a triplestore can be a complex process, as it involves using the SPARQL language,
296 with which many researchers are unfamiliar. This requires understanding how data is structured
297 into knowledge graphs, which are sets of RDF triplets: subject predicate object. For example, here
298 are two triplets:

```
300 louvre:ark:/53355/cl010257743 rdf:type crm:E22_Human-made_Object .  
301 louvre:ark:/53355/cl010257743 crm:P2_has_type pactols:ark:/26678/pcrt1tSmMf0Tw8 .
```

303 Writing a query in SPARQL is like expressing RDF triples. When known, this query language can
304 be used to trace the RDF triplets contained in the graph and obtain information according to the
305 desired result. The SPARQL endpoint enables any system or user to request the contents of a
306 triplestore.

307 But to do so, the ontological model with which the data is built must be understood, which is
308 also rarely the case for archaeologist users. The conceptualized model is based on key entities in
309 the field of archaeology, but the expression of these entities sometimes differs greatly in their
310 CIDOC CRM representation: a piece of an artefact becomes an entity in the E22 Human-Made
311 Object class, an archaeological features becomes an E25 Human-Made Feature entity and an
312 excavation/discovery becomes an S19 Encounter Event entity. In addition, CIDOC documentation
313 is mainly in English, which can be a barrier for archaeologists who are not fluent in English.
314 Translation work is underway (Krummeich, Guillem et al. 2024) to provide documentation in
315 French, in the hope that this will attract more French archaeologists. Nevertheless, it is essential
316 that the model be explained clearly and in detail in order to understand the modeling choices and
317 ease its usage. This documentation is available on the website, but will be refined as the platform
318 evolves. So, the user must be familiar with the concepts used in archaeology, and therefore be an
319 archaeologist. Furthermore this implies to being familiar with the ontology, the model, and the
320 interpretations chosen during the modelling step to understand how to query the knowledge graph
321 if SPARQL is chosen.

322 This is why an intuitive visual query interface was developed for OpenArcheo and then made
323 generic under the name Sparnatural by the company Sparna. The Sparnatural application is
324 developed in JavaScript and is open source. In OpenArcheo, Sparnatural is integrated into an

325 Explorer page, which allows cross-referencing all datasets, and into specific pages for each
326 dataset (search limited to the graph produced for that dataset). Sparnatural allows users to interact
327 with the triplestore without needing specific knowledge of the ontology, the underlying graph
328 model, or the SPARQL language. Users formulate visual queries as sentences describing what
329 they are looking for, with concepts that are clear for their domain. For instance in Figure 7, at the
330 top the user search for artefacts present on a site (upper part of the figure), and the system displays
331 the corresponding SPARQL query at the bottom. The query is launched with the play button.

332
333 **Figure 7** - Sparnatural query interface of the OpenArcheo platform.

334 Sparnatural implements this through a configuration file, written as an intermediate schema,
335 which maps each part of the knowledge graph to the view provided to user. Writing this
336 configuration requires all the knowledge from the modelling process, together with the key entities
337 of archaeology, defined during the modeling process of the OpenArcheo generic model. This
338 way, each CIDOC CRM class and their relationships can be translated according to the known
339 terminology of archaeology. For example, an object associated with the Human-Made Object class
340 in the generic CIDOC CRM model is reinterpreted, as conceptualized in the modeling, as an
341 artefact in the OpenArcheo portal. Sparnatural can then dynamically translate the artefact
342 selected by the user into the corresponding E22 Human-Made Object class and send the SPARQL
343 query shown in Figure 7 to the triplestore via its endpoint.

344 The same approach is applied to relationships, selecting relations such as "Artefact is dated
345 with a Date" which is then translated using the appropriate classes and properties to recreate the
346 path in the CIDOC CRM model. Thanks to this method, shortcuts are created, avoiding the
347 complexity of CIDOC CRM. The representation of the datation presented in Figure 2 adopts the
348 form more commonly used of a single property simply named "is dated" (Figure 8).

▼ Q Sparnatural explorer

SPARQL service : <https://openarchaeo-graphdb.huma-num.fr/repositories/openarchaeo> Select a query example ▼

Artefact is dated Date from 1200 to 1300

Show SPARQL editor | Export the query in JSON | Import a query in JSON

```

5 SELECT DISTINCT ?HumanMadeObject_1 ?HumanMadeObject_1_label WHERE {
6   ?HumanMadeObject_1 rdf:type crm:E22_Human-Made_Object.
7   OPTIONAL { ?HumanMadeObject_1 skos:prefLabel ?HumanMadeObject_1_label. }|
8   {
9     ?HumanMadeObject_1 ((crm:P8i_witnessed/crm:P4_has_time-span/crm:P82a_begin_of_the_begin)|
10    (^crm:P8_took_place_on_or_within/crm:P4_has_time-span/crm:P82a_begin_of_the_begin)) ?Z_Date_2_begin;
11    ((crm:P8i_witnessed/crm:P4_has_time-span/crm:P82b_end_of_the_end)|(^crm:P8_took_place_on_or_within/
12    crm:P4_has_time-span/crm:P82b_end_of_the_end)) ?Z_Date_2_end.
13    FILTER(?Z_Date_2_begin <= "1300-12-31T23:50:38Z"^^xsd:dateTime)
14    FILTER(?Z_Date_2_end >= "1199-12-31T23:50:40Z"^^xsd:dateTime)
15  }
16  UNION

```

Figure 8 - Example of an OpenArcheo query: artefact dated between 1200 and 1300.

349
350

351 Additionally, the configuration file also allows for better qualifications of the rather generic
352 CIDOC CRM model. An archaeological feature, although a key entity in the field, is often referred
353 to by a more specific term by which it is more commonly identified. The configuration interpret
354 using shared controlled vocabularies in the knowledge graph, that an E25 Human-Made Feature
355 of the type « burial » is a burial in the Sparnatural user interface (Figure 9). The concept « burial »
356 is taken from the Pactols thesaurus (Nouvel, 2021). Here we see all the benefits of linking
357 semantics to controlled vocabularies. It is the vocabulary from the Pactols thesaurus that specifies
358 the CIDOC Feature class (too generic for our needs), to clarify whether it is a burial, a wall or a pit.
359 The specification expected by the archaeologist is provided by the E55_Type class. Thus, to meet
360 an archaeological need, the controlled vocabulary enhances a concept deemed too generic in
361 CIDOC, without adding new classes to the model, which would reduce its interoperability. This
362 choice is the result of carefully considered compromises between, on the one hand, precision and
363 relevance for the discipline of archaeology and, on the other hand, the flexibility necessary to
364 ensure interoperability, by using CIDOC CRM, without modifying it.
365

▼ **Q Sparnatural explorer**

SPARQL service : <https://openarchaeo-graphdb.huma-num.fr/repositories/openarchaeo> Select a query example

Burial label Text Any

Show SPARQL editor | Export the query in JSON | Import a query in JSON

```

1 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
2 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
3 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
4 SELECT DISTINCT ?Burial_1 ?Burial_1_label ?Z_Text_2 WHERE {
5   ?Burial_1 rdf:type crm:E25_Human-Made_Feature;
6     crm:P2_has_type <https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrt795b632nWw>.
7   OPTIONAL { ?Burial_1 skos:prefLabel ?Burial_1_label. }
8   ?Burial_1 skos:prefLabel ?Z_Text_2.
9 }
10 LIMIT 1000

```

366
367
368

Figure 9 - In OpenArcheo, the concept of Burial is an E25 Human-made Feature specified by a Pactols type (ARK identifier of the "burial" concept).

369
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Controlled vocabularies and repositories are also used in Sparnatural to provide drop-down lists or completion fields. The labels of each concept are proposed to the user who, through a selection action, will add the URI of the concept to their query. This behavior of the tool once again makes the conceptualization around the modeling effective, as the use of controlled vocabularies is a way to perform cross-queries on datasets originally expressed in heterogeneous ways. In Figure 10, building a query in Sparnatural, "Artefact had as general use Coin," allows searching for all E22 Human-Made Object entities whose object of the property "P101 had as general use" is the Pactols concept of Coin. The result of the query includes objects identified in four datasets integrated into OpenArcheo.

▼ **Q Sparnatural explorer**

SPARQL service : <https://openarchaeo-graphdb.huma-num.fr/repositories/openarchaeo> Select a query example ▼

Artefact → had as general use → Type → coins → +

Show SPARQL editor | Export the query in JSON | Import a query in JSON

```

1 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
2 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
3 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
4 SELECT DISTINCT ?HumanMadeObject_1 ?HumanMadeObject_1_label WHERE {
5   ?HumanMadeObject_1 rdf:type crm:E22_Human-Made_Object.
6   OPTIONAL { ?HumanMadeObject_1 skos:prefLabel ?HumanMadeObject_1_label. }
7   ?HumanMadeObject_1 crm:P101_had_as_general_use <https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtaDZQ1TT058>.
8 }
9 LIMIT 1000

```

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Figure 10 - In OpenArcheo, a Coin is an E22 Human-made Object specified by a Pactols concept (ARK identifier of the "coin" concept).

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It is also possible through the drop-down list to select a specific concept present in several datasets, by aggregating occurrences from the same concept across different datasets (Figure 11). This functionality eases cross-querying for the user.

384
385 **Figure 11** - Sparnatural organization of concepts based on their presence in the datasets.

386 The installation and configuration of Sparnatural not only makes the content of the
387 OpenArcheo triplestore accessible but also highlights all the process that led to the creation of
388 the OpenArcheo generic model. Although these conclusions were already verifiable within the
389 triplestore using SPARQL queries, Sparnatural allows users unfamiliar with Semantic Web
390 technologies to verify for themselves the interoperability made possible by these technologies.
391 Last but not least, Sparnatural is also useful when updating the OpenArcheo model, which is built
392 and maintained using the eXtreme Design methodology (Blomqvist 2016), i.e. with a modular
393 approach, each module being able to answer some precise so-called competency questions.
394 Competency questions represent the needs for which an ontology is built (Wiśniewski 2019).
395 Modules are called Ontology Design Patterns in eXtreme Design. The OpenArcheo model's
396 patterns are identified and conceptualized in the Sparnatural configuration file, so that the adding
397 of classes and properties are directly interpreted to capture a new competency question previously
398 lacking in the model.

399 **IV- A web portal built around the Semantic Web**

400 OpenArcheo is not limited to integrate an instance of Sparnatural in its use of the Semantic
401 Web or using the knowledge graph modeled with the generic CIDOC CRM model. OpenArcheo
402 aims to be a catalog of datasets represented as linked open knowledge graphs, serving as a
403 gateway to the publications of these various originally siloed datasets (Figure 12).

404
405

Figure 12 - Catalog of datasets available in OpenArcheo in the explorer page.

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This catalog function implies that OpenArcheo must describe the datasets existing in the catalog using standardized metadata. In addition to the generic model extracted from CIDOC CRM, a description model using other standard vocabulary/ontology of the Semantic Web, such as Dublin Core Terms and Data Catalog Vocabularies (DCAT, a W3C standard), has been conceptualized to express the metadata of the datasets in RDF format (Figure 13).

412
413

Figure 13 - OpenArcheo presents the metadata related to each dataset in a specific page.

414 This method follows the FAIR principles for the formalization of the descriptions of the datasets
415 present in OpenArcheo, while maintaining openness with other aggregators, avoiding to use of
416 an ontology that would be solely functional for OpenArcheo.

417 Provenance metadata of the dataset (creator, publisher, creation date, source URL of the
418 dataset, etc.) are included, as well as contextual metadata (themes/subjects of the dataset, spatial
419 and temporal coverage, time interval covered by the dataset content, etc.). To maintain
420 consistency with the knowledge graph represented using the generic CIDOC CRM model, the
421 same controlled vocabularies and referentials are used in the metadata (PeriodO for temporal
422 coverage, GeoNames for spatial coverage, Getty AAT/Pactols for themes/subjects, and
423 VIAF/ORCID/IdRef for people/institutions). These choices allow for the cross-referencing of
424 datasets not only at the level of their content but also at the level of their description, on a page
425 dedicated to the [OpenArcheo catalog](#) (Figure 14).

Datasets

The screenshot displays the 'Datasets' section of the OpenArcheo catalog. On the left, there are three filter panels: 'Filters by keywords', 'Filters by periods', and 'Filters by places'. Each panel contains a list of terms with small circular icons indicating the number of datasets associated with each term. For example, 'Ancient Greek (culture or style) [AAT]' has 6 datasets, 'Greeks [Pactols]' has 5, and 'Antique, the [AAT]' has 2. The 'Filters by periods' panel shows 'Roman Empire' with 3 datasets and 'Middles Ages' with 2. The 'Filters by places' panel shows 'France' with 1 dataset and 'Cyprus' with 1. Below the filters are 'Show more' and 'Reset filters' buttons. On the right, there are six dataset cards, each with a title, a brief description, and metadata including 'Issued', 'Modified', and 'Triples' counts.

Dataset Title	Issued	Modified	Triples
Chronique des fouilles en ligne	2020-01-01	2025-11-26	492124
Conservatoire National des Données 3D	2019-01-01	2025-11-26	19675
EpiCherchell	2021-02-05	2025-11-26	15107
Kition-Pervolia	2020-10-01	2025-11-26	32434
Arkeogis - Syslat	2025-09-29	2025-11-26	1446
Arkeogis - Verduron	2022-05-25	2025-11-26	482

426
427

Figure 14 - Selection of datasets in OpenArcheo using filters.

428 The description of the datasets also includes information about the knowledge graph,
429 specifically the named graphs, which are unique to each dataset. Since OpenArcheo is an
430 aggregator using Semantic Web technologies, the specific endpoint for querying the named graph
431 of a dataset or the number of triples forming the named graph of the dataset are elements of the
432 description in the catalog. The [catalog description](#) is available for download in [JSON-LD](#) format,
433 one of the possible textual representations of RDF graphs.

V- Results

435 At the time of writing, the OpenArchaeo catalog describes 16 datasets, each stored in the
436 OpenArchaeo triplestore as a specific knowledge graph. These knowledge graphs comprise more
437 than 2 million explicit triples (without inferences), ranging from 800,000 for ArSol to fewer than 500
438 for Arkeogis – Verduron. Over 1,220 PACTOLS concepts and 5,000 GeoNames resources are
439 used across the graphs. At most, a single PACTOLS concept appears in 9 datasets, while a
440 GeoNames resource appears in up to 6. Considering the 8 main classes of the OpenArchaeo
441 generic model (presented in Figure 1), only ArSol covers all classes. Four datasets cover 7
442 classes, another four cover 6 classes, and the remainder cover 4 or 5 classes. These numbers are
443 encouraging: despite the thematic diversity of the datasets (e.g., site inventories, excavation
444 documentation, thematic databases), shared classes and concepts consistently appear across the
445 knowledge graphs.

446 For the future, the free version of GraphDB should be replaced with a more performant open-
447 source triplestore. Because while simple queries in Sparnatural return results in less than a second
448 (like the one presented in Figure 9), complex queries often time out or take several minutes. This
449 issue also stems from OpenArchaeo's federation system, which repeatedly queries the same
450 triplestore (since all graphs are stored there). A Sparnatural query across all 16 datasets translates
451 into 16 separate queries, yet GraphDB's freeware version processes only 3 concurrent queries,
452 causing bottlenecks and some time out.

VI- Conclusion

454 OpenArchaeo aims to provide to archaeologists a platform that utilizes semantic web
455 technologies to cross-examine various datasets through a SPARQL endpoint, while offering them
456 also an intuitive interface based on the Sparnatural application. The datasets are transformed to
457 knowledge graphs following a rigorous and well documented workflow. The first step in this
458 workflow is to understand the shared model devised for federating the dataset at the semantic
459 level. This model, an ontology called OpenArchaeo Model, is extracted from the CIDOC CRM and
460 some of its official extensions. The use of these standards, together with shared thesauri and other
461 reference system such as Geonames and PeriodO, makes the datasets interoperable in their
462 description and content, allowing for data cross-referencing within the platform. This is also the
463 base for integration with other national or international aggregators (such as Nakala, ARIADNE).

464 The OpenArchaeo platform enhances the value of research data by making it easily findable
465 and accessible, in accordance with the first FAIR principles. Furthermore, through the use of
466 semantic technologies and standard domain ontologies and thesauri, the presented data is
467 interoperable, and reusable via the triplestore endpoint and all the documentation added in the
468 portal. It is important to notice that, while the configuration file of the OpenArchaeo platform has
469 been devised for the archeology domain, the Sparnatural platform was thought as a universal
470 solution allowing the use of other models and the aggregation of other datasets. As this
471 configuration file and all the codes of the OpenArchaeo platform are publically available, they can
472 be adapted for other domains.

473 However, OpenArchaeo lacks feedback from the community to assess the relevance of the
474 Sparnatural configuration, improve the data aggregation process, and refine the query system to
475 enhance the platform, increase the number of available corpora, and the user base of these
476 corpora. The datasets already integrated are mostly produced by members and partners of
477 MASA+, and the platform would benefit from diversification and enrichment with additional
478 datasets. Although the generic model of OpenArchaeo has been presented and modified several
479 times, feedback still is welcome to making it evolve and meet the needs of the community. To this
480 end, we plan to perform a user-based evaluation in the form of an hackaton during a workshop.

481 After a few years of existence, OpenArchaeo does not yet have a sufficient data pool to make
482 it a reference and we must continue to integrate new datasets. Several corpora are currently being
483 integrated, but their processing requires rigor and time, as it relies on human expertise. We are

484 working to set up training courses and tutorials to help archaeologists get to grips with the workflow.
485 We are doing our utmost to lower the technological barrier so that the semantic web is not
486 considered too complex for most of our colleagues, particularly archaeologists who are in the field
487 and have little time to devote to these essential issues.

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492 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

493 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest
494 in relation to the content of the article.

495 **Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability**

496 The OpenArcheo portal is accessible here: <http://openarchaeo.huma-num.fr>

497 The code for the new version of the OpenArcheo portal is available on Huma-Num GitLab:
498 https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/masa/openarchaeo_sparnatural

499 it is also archived on the Software-Heritage platform:

500 <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:4564d25d7847ec77617fac4d51543214028c1c58>

501 and registered on HAL: <https://hal.science/hal-05563250>

502 The code for Sparnatural is available on the Sparna GitHub: [https://github.com/sparna-](https://github.com/sparna-git/Sparnatural)
503 [git/Sparnatural](https://github.com/sparna-git/Sparnatural)

504 Data is available on the OpenArcheo datasets page as knowledge graphs (e.g. for Aerba
505 <https://openarchaeo.huma-num.fr/portal/catalog/aerba>) and queryable in SPARQL here:
506 <https://openarchaeo.huma-num.fr/portal/sparql-endpoint>

507 The SHACL documentation of the OpenArcheo CIDOC-CRM model is available online here:
508 https://openarchaeo.huma-num.fr/portal/doc/html/OpenArcheo-Model_SHACL_fr.html

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